

GLTF SUITABILITY FOR DIGITAL HERITAGE 3D ASSETS

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Abstract. Digital Heritage, as a digitisation and dissemination process, involves collecting detailed data on tangible assets for preservation and knowledge sharing. However, the distribution of DH 3D assets faces several challenges, mainly caused by a lack of standardisation, i.e. minimum quality requirements, metadatation and publishing formats. Adopting a FAIR approach could help in characterising such needed standards, emphasising open-source formats, documented production pipelines and accessibility of online repositories that would rely on Web3D-Optimised formats to allow hardware and software neutrality. This paper focuses, in particular, on the importance of choosing an appropriate 3D model interchange format for 3D assets belonging to DH and subsequently proposes a critical review of the glTF format to prove its suitability to this need. glTF's open design, its extensible structure, flexibility, interoperability, and rapid development, supported by a JSON-Based structure and compatibility by-design with WebGL, are highlighted. Finally, a simplified and coherent feature list for glTF is provided, mainly focusing on the glTF PBR-Based material system, on the mutual interrelations between the parameters and on aggregating the features currently described by the relatively sparse and technical documentation in a diverse, more Final User-Oriented taxonomy where is highlighted the contribution of each feature to the overall glTF suitability as an effective 3D assets interchange format for the Digital Heritage.

Keywords: glTF, Digital Heritage, FAIR.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Digital Heritage

Of the current digital technologies for Cultural Heritage (CH) (Beacham, Denhardt & Niccolucci, 2006) [1], many are dedicated to its digitisation and dissemination by building and giving access to a digital transposition of the tangible assets of which it consists and are collectively encompassed under the definition of Digital Heritage (DH) (Lusenet, 2007) [2].

As the process of digitisation implies collecting data about tangible assets such as geometry, structure, materials and more, building a solid, detailed and data-rich DH, it is also pivotal for heritage preservation and its knowability (Gomes, Bellon & Silva, 2014) [3], both for the general public and for the scientific research and since also the tools used for inspecting, analysing and studying are based on a digital approach.

Fig.1 Logo of the recently published (2022) EU-commissioned survey and study about methods, practices and standards for the digitisation of CH <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/study-quality-3d-digitisation-tangible-cultural-heritage>.

Within the European context, DH has received significant attention, highlighted through various EU programs both in the present and the last programming, as the EU recognises the critical role of DH in preserving cultural legacies for future generations. Cultural Heritage Cloud (Brunet, de Luca, Hyvönen, et al., 2022) [4] aims to add a digital dimension to cultural heritage preservation, conservation, restoration, and enhancement by fostering a transdisciplinary collaboration among specialists from various disciplines.

The design of this data space includes a novel ontology that would be interoperable with other EU initiatives like Europeana (Valtysson, 2012) [5], a repository meant to work as a portal to access the DH and that has been designed to overcome the lack of metadata in the most used repositories worldwide. This initiative also focuses on making the data space accessible, participatory, and inclusive, thus ensuring that it is representative of and co-created by different

communities so that any preconception and bias about the specific value or importance of the tangible assets would be neutralised.

1.2 Web3D

Where the technological setup for working with and for DH in the scientific research and in the ecosystem of private business initiatives involved in the digitisation process mainly relies on dedicated professional software and hardware, any generic individual should be able to interact with it through personal devices, imposing a shift towards more user-friendly and accessible forms of cultural engagement that could “enhance citizens’ well-being through better cultural accessibility and inclusion” (Fanea-Ivanovici & Pană, 2020) [6].

The integration of DH into everyday technology, such as portable devices or consumer-level computers, should then primarily occur through web browsers without the need for further installations and where it is possible to leverage interface modalities that are already assimilated, like swiping, zooming, and panning rather than relying on dedicated applications that require an even minimal specific learning phase, have at least to be downloaded and installed on our already crowded desktops and rely on sub-optimal programming and technological implementation.

The ensemble of technologies and standards that allow this objective to fall within the generic definition of Web3D, whose journey dates back to the early 1990s with the development of the Virtual Reality Modeling Language (VRML) and is still ongoing nowadays

Web3D has become a vital part of the modern web, with applications ranging from online gaming to virtual reality and augmented reality (WebXR) and various forms of interactive web content. These are the necessary technological premises for making DH accessible to the general public

1.3 Assets and Repositories

However, the potential granted by Web3D for DH has yet to be wholly developed, since many key aspects have yet to be addressed with an even degree of effort and are still problematic. One such critical issue is the distribution of 3D assets central to DH, which faces challenges, especially regarding availability and quality of repositories.

Public repositories exist, but many, starting from Europeana, are sparsely populated and exhibit a highly variable quality of assets, as a study on the quality of 3D digitisation in tangible Cultural Heritage commissioned in 2020 EU has highlighted (Pritchard, Rigaut, Ripanti et. al., 2021) [7] (Fig.1). Along with several other problematic aspects, the critical issue lacks standardisation, particularly in formats, which impedes consistent quality and accessibility.

Hence, most DH assets use the most widely diffused commercial repositories, such as Sketchfab (Champion & Rahaman, 2020) [8] (Fig.2). Its reachability and state-of-the-art implementation of Web3D technologies and standards make it an almost inevitable choice for sharing high-quality 3D assets online.

Moreover, the lack of standards also implies the impossibility of stating a minimum quality level for the 3D assets themselves, whose compliance would determine whether a 3D asset is suitable to be part of DH, as it is intended to be.

Fig.2 “Triceratops Horridus Marsh” asset, as published by Smithsonian Institute on the online 3D-dedicated platform Sketchfab

1.4 A FAIR approach for Digital Heritage

It is then necessary to step back and delineate an array of characteristics that a 3D asset should have to comply with the stated purposes for DH. We believe that adopting a FAIR approach for DH would be necessary since it would involve crafting assets that are Findable and Accessible through possibly public repositories that would support a rich metadatation

(Barbuti, 2020) [9]. This same claim is supported by Barzaghi, Bordignon et al. (2024) [10], who integrate the glTF format into a FAIR-compliant management of the entire DCHO digitalisation process.

Furthermore, DH assets would need to be Interoperable, thus should leverage neutral open-source formats and be adaptable to various frameworks or applications, and eventually be Replicable, meaning that the pipeline for its production would be known, documented, standardisable and be followed entirely by using FOSS software.

1.5 Asset interchange formats

The first and critical challenge of this FAIR-based approach is identifying an appropriate interchange format for 3D models. Given the incompatibility of proprietary formats with WebGL, there is the need to look for a format that is readable by FOSS software but also implemented in proprietary commercial pipelines to allow the interchange of the assets stage between different software, even if there is no strict need to incorporate those complex features that are needed for the asset editing and preparation since the format should be suitable only for the final version of the 3D asset by supporting just the features requested by Web3D/WebXR applications and frameworks. Not needing further support, the format would also be lighter and easier to parse. Formats like OBJ and FBX have been and still are used as interchange formats but are proprietary.

OBJ was developed by Wavefront Technologies in the early 1980s as part of their Advanced Visualizer animation package. Over the years, the OBJ format's simplicity and adaptability have cemented its status as a common choice for 3D modelling and animation, even if it doesn't support complex features like animations or shaders.

Similarly, FBX was initially developed by a private company, Kaydara, that later became part of Autodesk. Introduced in 2001, FBX was designed as a platform-independent 3D data interchange format to facilitate higher-fidelity data transfer between various graphics software platforms, including simple and character animation. Since it became a standard, FBX is readable by almost any 3D software, even if not all of its features are needed for many applications.

COLLADA, which stands for "Collaborative Design Activity" and whose extension is DAE, was initially developed by Sony Computer Entertainment and then transferred to Khronos Group (Fig.3), a non-profit consortium with which Sony is affiliated. COLLADA is an open-standard XML-based format used to exchange digital assets and is notably able to preserve complex animations and physics data. As for FBX, it is more suitable to transfer data between different software in complex editing pipelines, even by being an open format.

This is why the same Khronos Group started in 2015 to work on Graphics Library Transmission Format (glTF), a brand new format whose specifications have been formulated to fill this niche in the technological ecosystem.

The present paper proposes a critical analysis of its features list (Khronos Group. 2023) [11] to assess its suitability as the standard format for publishing 3D assets belonging to the DH on Web3D-compliant platforms.

2. GLTF FILE FORMAT'S GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS

GLTF does not depend on a particular Application Programming Interface (API) for its implementation or use. This API neutrality makes GLTF flexible and interoperable, allowing developers to choose the tools and platforms that best suit their needs without adapting the format to the publishing options.

Being JSON-based, it inherits the interoperability, the ease of programming and debugging that comes from being human-readable, and the speed of parsing due to its simplicity and lightness, which make it particularly suitable to be read at runtime. Additionally, JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) data structure is very similar to the object structure in JavaScript and, like JavaScript, can be rendered directly on browsers without needing additional plugins, thanks to WebGL. It is also the language with which three.js is written, a widely used open-source library for creating and displaying interactive 3D computer graphics in web browsers using WebGL.

GlTF is therefore inherently optimised for WebGL, and through this to Web3 in general, being part of the coherent technological ecosystem centred on WebGL that Khronos Group has built and is keeping on improving based on the solid interrelation by the various interoperability standards it has developed.

It is worth noticing that even if glTF is not precisely "open source" in the proper sense, as it is a specification rather than a software implementation, the specification itself is freely available on GitHub and can be implemented by anyone without requiring any royalties or fees by using the CC-BY-4.0 license on the generated output documents.

GLTF development has been rapid. Since the publication of glTF 1.0 specifications, the major update glTF 2.0 followed after only two years in 2017, grating backwards and forward compatibility per design. Even if this is the latest major update, in the subsequent years, the format has been expanded at a fast pace thanks to its modular structure, whereby independent blocks of code called Extensions can be added to the core of the format.

Fig.3 GLTF and other formats handled by Khronos Group Inc. consortium, image retrieved from <https://www.khronos.org/about/> © Khronos Group Inc. CC by 4.0

GLTF Extensions can address any aspect of the format, such as improving materials by broadening the list of supported characteristics or scene entities, adding compatibility to specific formats or libraries, supporting compression formats, or even introducing completely new features or file diagnostics.

This is a compelling design by itself and is further enhanced as extensions can be either developed directly by Khronos Group or by external actors, usually vendors that need specific not-yet implemented features and hence develop them internally and, as the openness of the format imposes, have to document and share.

Extensions are typically written against a specific version of glTF and may be promoted to core glTF in a later glTF version. Thus, they can be considered temporary "patches" of the major format version waiting to be incorporated in subsequent releases but already providing added functionality.

3. GLTF'S FEATURES FOR A GENERALIST AUDIENCE

All the specifications for the format and all the extensions are fully available on GitHub. However, on the first hand, they are not meant to be read by programmers and hence are organised with a paratactic taxonomy that assesses importance levels as an effort-intensive task; on the other hand, specifications that concur to a single feature may be spread between the core format documentation and an extension's. Furthermore, since extensions are written against the format at least until they are incorporated in major releases, the same happens with documentation.

The diagram provides a comprehensive overview of the glTF format's structure and components. It is organized into several main sections:

- gltf - what the?**: Overview of the format, including its design goals and the role of the glTF 2.0 specification.
- Concepts**: Fundamental concepts like scenes, nodes, meshes, and materials.
- cameras**: Details on camera types (perspective, orthographic) and their properties.
- skins**: Information on how meshes are skinned, including joint matrices and weights.
- textures, images, samplers**: Explanation of how textures are referenced and processed, including image samplers and texture views.
- materials**: Detailed look at material properties, including the Metallic-Roughness model and various material extensions.
- buffers, bufferViews, accessors**: Explanation of how data is stored and accessed, including buffer targets and sparse accessors.
- animations**: Details on animation types (keyframe, procedural) and how they are applied to nodes.
- animation samplers**: Information on how animation samplers are used to retrieve animation data.
- animation target weights**: Details on how weights are used to blend between different animation targets.
- Material properties in textures**: Further details on material properties and how they are stored in texture data.
- Binary glTF files**: Information on how glTF data is serialized into binary files for efficient storage and transmission.

Fig.4 Schematic overview on glTF format, from [github.com/khronosgroup/glTF-Overview/](https://github.com/khronosgroup/glTF-Overview) © Khronos Group Inc. CC by 4.0

Then, it has given the case when, in the format documentation, a statement is changed or integrated elsewhere by the extension documentation.

Not being intended for a generalist reader, and despite the simplicity and readability of the code itself, official specifications may need to be more easily understood by a generalist public. At the same time, programmers who need to look into the specifications to build or customise an extension due to a specific need that might be posed by the application he or she is working at might miss some crucial details or conventions that might lead to unexpected behaviours when the glTF asset is.

If such problems are not highly important for extensions, they become relevant regarding the material system. As this paper will clarify, glTF uses the Physically Based Rendering (PBR) system, which is based on a large number of parameters that can be variously interdependent. In addition, other extensions might be built on other extensions, further complicating the task of building a clear general view of the format features.

For all these reasons, this paper provides a simplified and coherent feature list for glTF (Fig. 4) built by aggregating and reorganising all the official documentation in a manner intended to be easier to parse, even for a generalist reader who would need to know if and how to use glTF for authoring and publishing a 3D asset for DH.3.2 Structure and conventions.

glTF is not limited to a single asset as it can contain many of them, including lights, cameras, and environments. The basic structure of the format consists of two files: a .glTF file that contains only text describing the scene, all the characteristics of the elements in the scene itself and relative paths for reference to large resources such as geometry, animations, and other buffer-based which are instead contained in the second binary file with the extension .bin, since if they were stored inside the JSON file they would have to be stored as text strings, taking up much more space.

Image files are stored separately, either as .png or .jpeg, and no other format is supported. Neither is any ICC profile, which will consequently be discarded, assuming that all RGB colours are mapped in a linear space. Additionally, .png files cannot contain animation and must have a square-pixel ratio.

The .glTF has a node hierarchy, with the scene node as the root level. A glTF can contain 0, 1, or more scene nodes, each of which can be further organised with other specialised nodes following the same hierarchy.

glTF format includes an extensive list of features that, starting from an optimisation-by-design approach to the use of hardware resources, make it possible to employ most of the techniques used in the film and video game industry to create realistic and engaging 3D assets, integrating them with additional tools to exploit the potential of Web 2.0 such as interactive 3D configurators and e-commerce.

Where such features have been specifically conceived for the creation of high-quality 3D assets natively compatible with Web3D technologies in such a way as to increase their use and dissemination by private commercial actors, read from the perspective of scientific research and public decision-makers, they constitute at a technical level an optimal vehicle for the dissemination of both native and digitised digital assets. Similarly, the open approach of the format, which was constitutively decided to speed up its adoption and incentivise private actors to contribute to its development in a sort of crowdsourcing, also makes it potentially FAIR compliant and thus removes the possible ethical and methodological obstacle to its adoption that the use of a proprietary format would constitute for the public actor itself.

The following subsections provide the non-specialist reader with a reasoned, systematic and punctual overview of the characteristics of the glTF format, hitherto described more generically concerning the context, organising them into homogeneous clusters and describing the main parameters employed and paying particular attention to the characteristics dedicated to the materials, since it is these that determine the perceived visual quality of the 3D asset and by this way improve the final user engagement: Geometry and animation (3.1); Textures (3.2); Materials (3.3); 3D Scene, compression, compatibility (3.4).

3.1 Geometry and animation related features

Any node can have TRS transformations applied with Rotation in radians, Translation in meters, and Scale following a right-handed coordinate system. It can be instanced, with each instance having its own TRS transformation.

Each 3D asset is referenced by one of these specialised nodes called "mesh" node, which supports morph targets and can be skinned via another dedicated node. Each mesh is internally subdivided into separated entities called "primitives," which are the entities that contain all the properties supported by the geometry.

Besides the banal XYZ position, glTF primitives support vertex normals and tangent. The former allows specifying a pre-calculated normal direction for each vertex different from the local average, which is crucial for the correct shading of low-poly assets, and the latter supports the application and rendering of NormalMaps.

With regard to animation, a primitive can be linked to one or more joints, and its components can be skinned by weighting the influence of any of the joints connected. A primitive can also have multiple morph targets, which are supported by weighting the addition of primitives' attributes in the target mesh to the correspondent attributes in the base mesh.

3.2 Texture related features

Mesh primitives are eventually characterised also by properties for texturing and colouring with vertex colour. The latter might be of secondary importance for a generalist use since rendered colour is mainly handled by material properties, but it is crucial for DH assets to convey and showcase heatmaps obtained by mesh inspection, quality assessment, confidence, density or any other mesh diagnostic computed in specialised software like MeshLab or CloudCompare.

glTF primitives support UV coordinates for one or more UV sets. This support includes different tiling options (repeat, mirror and clamp) and allows for rotation and scaling of the texture by manipulating the image used.

As mentioned before, the only image formats supported are .jpeg, webp, and .png. However, PNG is preferable for many reasons, starting from its support for an Alpha channel, which many material features use. It has to be taken into account that glTF does not consider any associated ICC profile, assuming colours are always coded in a linear space. Client implementations are suggested to resize all non-power-of-two image dimensions, and this means that it is safer to consider that glTF uses only square images with the canonic power-of-two dimensions.

3.3 Materials related features

glTF materials are inherited from the PBR system and its key principles: energy conservation, microfaceting theory and Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution function (BRDF).

The PBR in glTF is centred around the Metalness/Roughness (M/R) model for its adaptability, high degree of realism (Fig. 5), and consistency across platforms. The setup of M/R is the minimum requirement for a material to be rendered, while all other behaviours are optional and can be defined to interact and enrich the base model.

Fig.5 Realistic “DamagedHelmet” from Khronos glTF Viewer <https://github.khronos.org/glTF-Sample-Viewer-Release/>

While some of these parameters' values are purely numeric, the majority are defined by the product of a raster map and a factor (M+F). When no image is loaded as a map, it is assumed that its value is pure white anyway, so the resulting value is defined by the factor alone for the entire material.

In order to optimise the amount of data and, consequently, its loading speed, glTF employs only one colour channel of the image used as a map to describe a given parameter, thus allowing several parameters to be controlled with a single image using the four available channels R, G, B and A. As will be specified later, this strategy is currently only used for Metalness (Blue), Roughness (Green), and opacity (Alpha), while the Red channel is left free to describe with the same map a fourth parameter of your choice among the many that are controlled by this channel.

Should the material require further parameters to be described by the Red channel, the strategy is also effective for additional images that are to be saved. In particular, for those saved in .png format, its lossless compression is most effective with repetitive or low-complexity data, and thus, the two residual colour channels at zero become an advantage in size, however small.

The core Physical Based Rendering model: Metalness/Roughness and Specular

As previously anticipated, the backbone of PBR implementation in glTF is the M/R model, which is determined only by 3 parameters: base colour, Metalness and Roughness. This setup changed slightly as new extensions were added to the format specifications.

The Roughness parameter is controlled by the Green channel of an image and its factor; a resulting Roughness of 0 is rendered as a perfect lucid material, while a Roughness of 1 corresponds to a perfect Lambertian material. Metalness is controlled by the Blue channel and its factor; when Metalness is 1, the material is rendered as a purely metallic object, while with Metalness 0, it is rendered as a pure dielectric (Fig.6). Any intermediate value for Metalness is rendered as a blend of the two models.

Within this framework, for a purely metallic BRDF, the primary determinant of the reflection colour at zero incidence is the colour itself, as defined by the BaseColour parameter, with roughness being the secondary factor. Conversely, a purely dielectric BRDF (dBRDF) in this system is formed by the combination of a diffuse BRDF, which utilizes the BaseColour for diffused light, and a specular BRDF, where the roughness parameter impacts specular reflections. Typically, these specular reflections default to white and are influenced by the light source. However, they can be altered via the Fresnel function, driven by a user-set Index of Refraction (IOR). The default IOR value is set around 1.5 but is adjustable from 1 to 2.

Moreover, glTF also enables the alteration of the specular reflection using two couples of M+F: one for the specular intensity and the other for the specular colour. These parameters also have feedback on the BaseColour of the dBRDF since, due to the energy conservation principle, the light energy transformed into a specular reflection is subtracted from the amount received by the underlying base layer for the orthogonal direction f_0 . At the same time, f_0 is unaffected and remains always white.

Fig.6 The M/R texture map of the asset "Damaged Helmet" from <https://github.com/KhronosGroup/glTF-Sample-Assets/tree/main/Models>

Non-opaque materials handling: Alpha, Transmission and Volume

Similarly to what occurred with M/R becoming deeply connected with specular and ior, Transmission and Volume extensions are bound to the core Alpha feature, making it easier to understand each feature along with the others.

The alpha channel of the same image used for M/R can be used with 3 distinct operational modes, all of which are also controlled by a factor. In the Opaque setting, alpha is not used, while in the Mask configuration, a user-controlled threshold determines whether the mesh will be locally rendered or not. Eventually, in the Blend mode, the mesh has a variable opacity following the values indicated by the alpha channel. Alpha should not be used to describe transparency as it simply governs the mesh, while proper physical transparency is determined by two dedicated subsets of parameters: transmission and volume.

Transmission assumes that the mesh represents an infinitely bubble-like thin layer, so no refraction or light absorption in the volume is expected. Transmission governs just the amount of light that is passed to underlying levels by using a

factor and the Red channel of an image as a Transmission map, making it one of the parameters that could use the free Red slot in the main M/R map for optimization.

The tinting effect implied by transmission is not influenced by transmission parameters itself since BaseColour is used instead for material coherence and parsimony. Also, the Roughness value influences how transparency is rendered, proportionally blurring both the objects seen through the mesh and the specular reflections that occur on the surface. With this respect, even if ior is not taken into account, it nonetheless influences the way it is scattered by the dBRDF at grazing angles. It has to be taken into consideration that the mBRDF part of a non purely dielectric material is not affected by transparency.

It is noteworthy that transparency rendering output is highly influenced by the client implementation of glTF and can lead to inconsistent outputs between different applications regarding the rendering of the background and objects seen through the transparent mesh. This issue can only be tackled at the programming level by introducing several stacked transparency.

Where ior is decisive is the Volume subset (Fig. 7), which allows the control of Refraction and light Absorption in the volume contained by the mesh, posing the manifoldness of the mesh as a prerequisite. Volume does not render Sub Surface Scattering (SSS) nor translucency since these are in-volume interactions that depend on the real distance covered by a light ray inside the medium, and glTF assets are primarily meant to be rendered in WebGL, which does not implement real-time raytracing.

Nonetheless, both Refraction and Absorption depend on the distance covered by light within the medium, so to be rendered realistically, this distance has to be previously specified. This task is accomplished for Refraction by controlling the feature with the Green channel of M+F, while for light Absorption by two numerical values: an absorption distance, which is the average distance light has to travel inside the medium before being absorbed, and an absorption colour, which is the colour the light assumes as it interacts with the medium. Both parameters are influenced by the material Roughness.

Fig.7 Interaction of Transmission and Volume extensions for the asset “MosquitoInAmber” from <https://github.com/KhronosGroup/glTF-Sample-Assets/tree/main/Models> Caption from Khronos glTF Viewer <https://github.khronos.org/glTF-Sample-Viewer-Release/>

Advanced physical based behaviours: Clearcoat, Iridescence, Anisotropy, Sheen, Self-lit

The Metalness/Roughness/Specular complex and the Alpha/Transmission/Volume one are sufficient to describe most materials. For the remaining, glTF also implements dedicated features. A first subgroup of features is formed by peculiar physical characteristics of materials. Within this sub-group, Clearcoat describes the behaviour of a thin transparent layer on top of other levels. It is controlled by two RGB M+F couples, one for layer Thickness and the other for Roughness, with the addition of a dedicated NormalMap.

Iridescence (Fig. 8), if used, is layered just below the Clearcoat and is dedicated to render the subtle hue variations induced by internal diffraction within a thin layer. As for Clearcoat, Iridescence has to be used wisely since it is defined by 6 parameters: a couple M+F where only the Red channel is used for Iridescence intensity, then a RGB thickness texture

that controls the variation between the minimum and the maximum thickness parameters and eventually a specific ior for the Iridescence layer.

Anisotropy is used to render how the light is reflected in a material by microfacets with a dominant orientation, causing reflections to be "stretched" along a specific direction. In glTF implementation, Anisotropy is controlled by all 3 colour channels of a dedicated map where Blue controls the overall intensity, while Green and Red describe the intensity respectively along the tangent direction and its orthogonal on the tangent plane. A third parameter is numerical and allows the rotation of the two orthogonal directions with respect to the tangent vector.

Sheen is layered right below the Clearcoat at the same level as Iridescence, being an alternative to it. Sheen simulates the back-scattering at grazing incidence of fabrics-like materials caused by microfibers of the surface and is controlled by two couples of M+F parameters, one for the intensity and the other for the sheen colour. The two maps are contained within a single image since Colour is described by RGB channels and intensity by Alpha channel.

Emissive allows the rendering of self-lit materials. Emissive is controlled by a couple of RGB M+F parameters, whose effect can be incremented by a third parameter in the form of a further factor which has been implemented to overcome the limitation to 8-bit images which could be not sufficient to render higher light intensities.

Fig.8 Example of advanced material features (Iridescence) for the asset "IridescenceAbalone" from <https://github.com/KhronosGroup/glTF-Sample-Assets/tree/main/Models> Caption from Khronos glTF Viewer <https://github.khronos.org/glTF-Sample-Viewer-Release/>

Other material-related features: NormalMaps, Ambient Occlusion, Double sided, Unlit

A second subgroup handles all expeditious methods typically used in Computer Graphics to overcome the limitations imposed by adopting an approximation to describe physical reality.

NormalMap is a fundamental implementation in Computer Graphics that can store all the surface irregularity features of a material with a level of detail superior to what geometry itself could describe. In a NormalMap, each colour channel describes the orientation in the space of detail's normals along the three local axes, with the Green channel being implemented in two alternative versions so that the user should check if the 3D software used for editing uses the option consistent with OpenGL conventions (+Y) or not (-Y)

Ambient Occlusion is used to factor the contribution of indirect environmental light to the rendered albedo of an asset. Hence, it does not affect direct in-scene lights that might be used. It is controlled by a couple M+F where only the Red channel of the image is used, making AO one of the candidates for occupying the free Red channel slot left by Metalness, Roughness and Alpha in the main map.

Double Sided is a yes/no status that determines whether the mesh faces seen from below the 3D surface of the mesh have to be rendered following the shading determined by the positive face of the mesh.

Unlit is another yes/no status that determines whether lighting affects the surface. In the latter case, the rendered albedo is uniquely determined by the BaseColor texture, and all other parameters' effect is zeroed. This provides a valuable

feature for assets whose albedo has been acquired from a tangible item by SfM photogrammetry, 3D scanning, or another survey technique typically used for DH assets.

3.4 Scene-related, Compression, format compatibility and other.

Lastly, we would also briefly recall other remaining features, with an augmented consideration for those that might be relevant for the implementation of glTF in the DH, starting from the support of .xmp format for embedded and customisable metadata, a relevant characteristic unique to the glTF format in respect to other asset interchange formats.

Concerning scene building, glTF supports in-scene cameras and lights, which can alternatively be Directional, Point or Spot. For the last two types, .ies files can be used to describe light's intensity variation along all the possible directions with respect to the position and orientation of the light source.

Alternatively, to in-scene lights, the meshes within a glTF can be lit by Image Based Lighting (IBL) .hdr maps, which are highly beneficial to the realistic level of the rendered output while showcasing or inspecting a glTF asset. It is noteworthy that repositories like Sketchfab provide internal browser-based authoring tool for scene editing and, hence, it is often convenient not to embed scene-related entities within the glTF. Furthermore, glTF implements advanced compression capability by supporting .ktx format and Draco.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The programmatic objectives underlying the design for the glTF format are consistent with the functional requirements for publishing 3D assets belonging to Digital Heritage. In fact, the glTF format is:

- efficient, in that it is lightweight and natively WebGL-compatible due to its Javascript-based definition;
- open, being fully documented and customisable;
- universal, since it is widely used and compatible with most 3D software, starting with FOSS tools;
- metadataable, thus granting complete and embedded documentation;
- flexible, since it allows the storage of additional scalar values such as heatmaps, confidence, etc., in the form of vertex colours, and this is an opportunity not yet delved into, nonetheless with great potential for scientific documentation

Additionally, due to its retro- and forward compatibility, which are mandated by design, it is also highly resistant to obsolescence. Hence, any new implementation or even a major release would not cause the deprecation of any previously introduced feature and, consequently, would not impair the fruition of already published content even if the application employing it had ceased to be supported and updated.

For all these reasons, and for its full compatibility with the framework Aton, glTF is the format chosen by Cultural Heritage Active innovation for Nex-Gen Sustainable Society (CHANGES) Extended Partnership for its pilot study for the digital-twin of the temporary exhibition “L' altro Rinascimento” held in Bologna from 12/08/2022 until 05/28/2023 (Balzani, Barzaghi, Bitelli, et al., 2023) [12].

However, although it can potentially support a high level of realism and high consistency between different rendering systems due to the PBR-based material system, glTF is still a relatively underused format, probably because its characteristics are not immediately understandable due to the high degree of optimisation in particular in the use of maps. This paper aims to attack this latter aspect by presenting the salient features of the format in a condensed manner and with a view to its use for Digital Heritage.

The features' clustering and mutual relationship proposed in the present work are purposely based on the field of application of a given glTF's feature rather than on technical similarity in a strict sense. Besides the apparent explanatory function, the scope of such an approach has been to provide a solid framework that could allow the categorisation of forthcoming features as well, leaving the extensive and continuously updated documentation.

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